

Relationship between Teachers' Competencies and Learners' Achievement of Linguistic Skills: A case of Public Secondary schools in Bungoma County, Kenya

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Abstract

In spite of the efforts to enhance the performance of English in Kenyan secondary schools, there have been persistent challenges in using the integrated English approach on learning achievement of linguistic skills. The aim of this paper was to determine the relationship between teachers' competencies and learners' achievement of linguistic skills in secondary schools in Bungoma County, Kenya. The study utilized descriptive research design using mixed methods approach. A sample size of 251 teachers, 371 students and 134 heads of the languages department was used. Purposive, proportionate and simple random sampling techniques were used to obtain the respondents. Data was collected using questionnaires and interview schedules. The validity of the instrument was tested through expert judgment while reliability was achieved using Cronbach Alpha. Quantitative data was analyzed by use of frequencies and percentages. Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Qualitative data was analyzed thematically and presented in narrations and quotations. The study found out that there was a positive correlation between teachers' competencies and learners' acquisition of linguistic skills ($r=.363$; $p=.000$). The study concluded that enhanced teacher competencies lead to learners' achievement of linguistic skills; writing, reading, speaking and listening. The study recommended that teachers of English at all levels need to enhance their competencies. The findings of this study will be significant to teachers of English to re-evaluate their teaching competencies and improve on them. It may also assist curriculum planners and developers at Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) on the need to organize in-service courses for teachers of English in line with the revised curriculum. Besides, it may assist the educators in the university and teachers training colleges in preparing the teachers of integrated English curriculum and harmonize their programme with the changing trends in teaching of English.

Key words: Relationship, Teachers' Competencies, Learners, Achievement, Linguistic Skills

1.0 Introduction

Language skills are significant when they are considered in the context of a language classroom. Several researches have been conducted worldwide to look for the efficacy of language skills and several approaches have been used for the purpose of integration of skills (Bastias, Sepulveda, Munoz & Lorena, 2011). As noted by Chen (2007), language skills should be integrated by the teacher in writing, reading, speaking and listening processes. All the language skills should be considered as inseparable, interdependent and integrated elements of a language. This is important because a language cannot be taught by merely focusing on one perspective, or one or few skills of language. In order to ensure effective learning of a language, all the skills should be taken into account and considered just as important as any other language skill. It is therefore considered essential on part of the teacher to integrate language skills in a language classroom. The best way to do so is by responding to the students either verbally or through written comments as they are reading or writing a text. It helps the learners to absorb and get hold of the comments, they will thus learn more as they put effort into comprehending the comments. However, teachers' competencies may hinder learners' achievement of linguistic skills.

There are four elementary language skills which include listening, speaking, writing and reading. A learner in any language setting acquires his/her first language in this normal order and it is a fact that writing is considered the most intricate skill to achieve (Ellis, 2003). Further, Willis and Willis (2007) characterized speaking as an interactive skill and writing as the transactional skill. The first language is acquired practically without any struggle. In cases where there is learning of a second language additional to one's mother tongue, the state of affairs tends to be different in comparison to any specific mother tongue. Learning approaches can be said to be an individual's preferred way to acquire and use one's natural capabilities to emphasize specific ways to learn in a distinctive way.

Most studies have dwelt on examined the effects of reading comprehension on the development of reading skills and learners particularly from poor socio-economic backgrounds and those taught through the use of teacher centered methods may have challenges in the achievement of reading skills (Klauda & Guthrie, 2015; Guthrie & Klauda, 2014). Whereas these struggling students may attain poor scores in academic performance, due to their low self-esteem, their disentanglement in form of determination, for instance,

may influence their reading command and, thus may not gain skills of comprehension efficiently (Klauda & Guthrie, 2015).

Greater achievement of reading skills' achievement can be achieved when students master the concepts of reading achievement which include, logographic, alphabetic and orthographic phases (Magoma, 2016). Furthermore, vision word analysis could be less emphasized by teachers during learning of reading comprehension but still existing in it as at the preceding, orthographic phase where students create a methodical, instant and non-visual scrutiny of words. Undoubtedly, though, decrypting is seen to be an important part for achievement of reading skills in developmental representations of reading.

Development of written communication is among the competence aims of the Upper Secondary School English subject curriculum in Norway and, in common with other countries feedback and assessment for learning (AfL) have been encouraged in Norwegian schools (Bueie,2015; Gamlem & Smith, 2013; Røyeng, 2010). Feedback has been employed in formative assessment to promote the development of students' writing skills (Black & Wiliam, 2009) and AfL has been defined as a classroom practice that involves dialogue and feedback loops between teachers and peers during subject specific problem solving (Gamlem & Munthe, 2014). New digital technologies open up opportunities by providing automated feedback and specifically for enhancing the development of students' writing skills in English (Winerip, 2012).

Ohno (2011) contends that linguistic skills are the capability to identify and yield the characteristic linguistic structures and to efficiently use them during communication and the capability to assume linguistic forms including words, sounds and sentence structure. It is concerned with the acquisition of the linguistic code itself which includes syntax, lexicon and semantics. On the other hand, Canale and Swain as cited in Ohno, (2011) noted that grammatical skills is a key concern for any communicative method whose aims include providing students with knowledge of how to establish and prompt precisely the exact connotation of sounds. They trust that having knowledge of these guidelines is important in interpreting sounds for social connotation, particularly where there is a low degree of transparency between the literal meaning of a sound and the speaker's meaning.

The process of practicing speaking among students and their peers increases their confidence in speaking some words without worries. Besides that, learning in groups will improve their vocabulary mastery (Argawati, 2014). In addition, Zyoud (2016) role play is a familiar procedure that is typically applied in the classroom to improve students' speaking skill. In

role plays, learners are assigned roles and put into circumstances that they may ultimately encounter outside the classroom. Since role plays emulate life, it helps students to develop real life speaking skills by imagining and assuming the roles where they create a pretend situation, and they pretend to be some different persons.

As noted by Chastain as quoted in Gilakjani and Sabouri (2016) the aim of listening skills is to understand linguistics at ordinary speed in an unconscious situation. Moreover, Hamouda (2013) pointed out that listening as a skill is very significant in the acquisition of understandable input. In addition, Pourhosein and Ahmadi (2011) articulated that listening plays a significant part in the communication procedure. These researchers noted that listening is considered as the most vital skill among the four important parts of communication skills.

The practice by teachers in instruction during the integrated English and literature curriculum in Kenya has also been assessed by Manyasi (2014). Her study specifically concentrates on how cultural values in the set book; *The River and the Source* are taught via the integrated approach. Manyasi identifies a lack of integration of linguistic skills of speaking, listening, writing and reading in the teaching process. While teachers might fall short of integrating English and Literature skills appropriately as identified by Manyasi, the study goes further to find out whether professional development programs are effective enough to reduce such problems of integration. Integration is a way of assimilation of two independent but linked entities so as to reinforce and augment them. For instance, instructors of English in secondary schools can use short stories, novels, plays and poetry to augment the grammar instructions. Nevertheless, the goal of this research was on the usage of an integrated English approach on learners' linguistic development of skills in public secondary schools. Via acquaintance with literature, the student will enhance their English linguistic skills (KIE, 2006). Grammar can also be instructed by use of non-literary and literary materials thus instruction of grammar in context.

Gichuki (2007) notes that the quality of a student's acquisition is dependent on the quality of instructors' input. The instructor's competence therefore affects the quality of academic performance at the end of the syllabus. He further observed that instructors implementing the revised English curriculum in public secondary schools still had inadequate knowledge on integration and that some ideas were challenging to teach. Education level determines the quality of teachers in a school which in turn has an effect on students' achievement. Adeogun (2001) noted that the value of any education system worldwide is dependent on the quality of

the teaching staff. This is further supported by other researchers such as Rivkin et al., (2005), Harris & Sass, (2008) Adeyemi, (2014) and Aaronson *et al.*, (2007), who reported that school-based predictors of learners' achievement was the quality of teachers.

2.0 Methodology

The research used descriptive survey design using mixed approach methods. Mixed methodology is the blending of two or more approaches in a research study resulting in both quantitative and qualitative data (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011). The study was mixed methods in a single research which permits for pragmatism.

The study targeted all the 724 teachers of English teaching Form three students in 206 secondary schools in Bungoma County. In addition, the study targeted all heads of languages departments in all the 206 secondary schools. Form three teachers of English were specifically targeted for the purpose of this research because, it is at this level that set books are fully introduced according to the syllabus and thus the teacher is tasked with the responsibility of teaching the skills appropriately using an integrated approach. The sample size formula for this study is Krejcie and Morgan (1970) as quoted by Kasomo (2001) where a sample size of 251 teachers and 134 heads of the languages department was obtained.

The researcher stratified the respondents into the six administrative units; Bungoma Central sub-county, Bungoma East Sub-county, Bungoma West sub-county, Bungoma North sub-county, Bungoma south Sub-county and Mount Elgon Sub-county making Bungoma County. The researcher further employed a stratified sampling technique to select the respondents from each of the administrative units. Thereafter, simple random sampling was used to choose Form Three teachers of English involved in the study from each of the six administrative units. In addition, HODs in every selected school were selected purposely to take part in the study.

Questionnaires and interview schedules were the main data collection instruments used in this study. A pilot study was carried out in neighboring Kakamega County to establish the reliability of the research instrument. The content and structural validity of the instrument was tested through expert judgment while reliability was tested using the test-retest method. A correlation coefficient of equal or more than 0.70 was considered adequate to allow the researcher to proceed with the study as per the recommendations of Creswell (2014).

The quantitative data from the questionnaire was first subjected to preliminary processing through validation, coding and tabulation in readiness for analysis with the help of the

statistical package for social science (SPSS) computer package. Frequencies and percentages were used to analyze quantitative data. Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Qualitative data was thematically classified and arranged before they were reported in narrations and quotations as per the research objectives. Data analysis was presented by use of tables and figures.

3.0 Results and Discussions

The aim of this study was to determine the relationship between teachers' competencies and learners' achievement of linguistic skills. To achieve this objective, teachers of English were requested to rate their level of agreement on five-point Likert scale items on the effect of their competencies in the adoption of an integrated English approach. The results of the analyzed data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Teachers' Responses on Effect of Competencies in the Adoption of Integrated English Approach

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		Overall percentages
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Teachers have poor competence in oral literature	41	17.3	43	18.1	76	32.1	77	32.5	64.6
Teachers have inadequate knowledge on the teaching of English language using drama making the acquisition of speaking and writing concepts difficult	22	9.3	46	19.4	55	23.2	114	48.1	71.3
Intensive language training amongst teachers has enhanced the acquisition of the speaking, writing and listening skills	58	24.5	93	39.2	42	17.7	44	18.6	63.7
Teachers have been equipped with the relevant drama knowledge through in-service training	82	34.6	71	30.0	46	19.4	38	16.0	64.6
In-service training of teachers has enabled them acquire new methods of handling teaching of oral literature using drama	67	28.3	120	50.6	12	5.1	38	16.0	78.9

Table 1 shows that 77(32.5%) teachers of English were strongly in agreement with the statement that teacher's poor competence in oral literature, 76(32.1%) teachers agreed with the statement and 43(18.1%) teachers disagreed with the statement while 41(17.3%) teachers strongly disagreed with the statement. The results showed that the majority (64.6%) of the

teachers of English in secondary schools in Bungoma County reported that teachers had poor competence in oral literature. This negatively influences students' achievement of speaking skills. Gichuki (2007) noted that the quality of a student's acquisition of linguistic skills is dependent on the quality of an instructor's input and therefore instructor's capabilities affect the quality of achievement at the end of the course. This implied that since most teachers may be challenged in oral literature, the achievement of linguistic skills among learners may be difficult.

On the statement that teachers have inadequate knowledge on the teaching of English language using drama making the acquisition of speaking and writing concepts difficult, 114(48.1%) teachers strongly agreed, 55(23.2%) teachers agreed with the statement and 46(19.4%) teachers disagreed with the statement while 22(9.3%) teachers strongly disagreed with the statement. From the results, it emerged therefore that a majority (71.3%) of the teachers of English were of the view that the inadequacy of teachers' knowledge on the teaching of English language using drama had hindered students' acquisition of writing and speaking skills. Drama enhances authentic and spontaneous linguistic acquisition in contrast to the written language that can naturally be found in a typical language classroom (Piazzoli, 2011).

Further, 93(39.2%) teachers disagreed with the statement that intensive language training amongst teachers had enhanced the acquisition of the speaking, writing and listening skills, 58(24.5%) teachers strongly disagreed with the statement, 44(18.6%) teachers strongly agreed with the statement while 42(17.7%) teachers disagreed with the view. The responses pointed out that the majority (63.7%) of the teachers believed that intensive language training amongst teachers had not enhanced the acquisition of the speaking, writing and listening skills. This emanated from the fact that most of the teachers in the County had not undergone any specialized training or in-service training on the teaching of integrated English. This is consistent with the work of Matere (2012) who pointed out that training at pre-service and in-service levels, in addition to the consultative process of curriculum development was needed to prepare instructors to adapt to the rapid changes in the teaching of integrated English courses. In addition, Oseno, Barasa and Omulando (2014) on their study on challenges of teaching speaking skills by use of integrated approach in secondary schools in Kenya found out that teachers of English were experiencing some challenges in using the IA owing to their inadequate training in handling the content of integrating English and Literature.

In addition, 82(34.6%) teachers strongly disagreed with the statement that teachers had been equipped with the relevant knowledge through in-service training to enable them to handle drama, poetry, oral literature and grammar, 71(30.0%) teachers disagreed with the statement and 46(19.4%) teachers agreed with the statement while 38(16.0%) teachers strongly agreed with the view. The results showed that the majority (64.6%) of the teachers in public secondary schools had not undergone any in-service training and therefore lacked the necessary skills to enable them to handle drama, poetry, oral literature and grammar. This implied that apart from the normal teacher training in Universities, teachers need to undergo in-service training on pedagogies of teaching integrated English. Teachers need to have continued professional development for effective service delivery especially where new curriculum has been introduced (Day & Sachs, 2004).

Similarly, 120(50.6%) teachers disagreed with the statement that in-service training of teachers had enabled them to acquire new methods of handling teaching of oral literature using drama, 67(28.3%) teachers strongly disagreed, 38(16.0%) teachers strongly agreed while 12(5.1%) teachers agreed. From the responses, it was shown that the majority (78.9%) of the secondary school teachers had not undergone in-service training and were therefore not in a position to efficiently handle the teaching of oral literature using drama. Spoken literature has been documented as an important instrument for instruction of linguistic skills. This is consistent with the reviewed English syllabus which necessitates that instructors efficiently address the aims of integrated English language instruction (KIE, 2006). Spoken literature therefore offers one such setting for instruction of grammar and therefore teachers need to undergo in-service training to enable them to be effective in their teaching and enable learners to acquire linguistic skills.

On interviewing HODs, most of them agreed that teachers had been equipped with relevant knowledge in teaching integrated English through in-service training which had enabled them to acquire methods of handling the teaching of oral literature and drama. However, the in-service trainings are not regularly organized thus impeding on teachers' competencies in acquiring skills on emerging issues in integrated English. This is consistent with the work of Harrell (2010) who reported that many teachers are not competent to teach integrated science curriculum due to their insufficient content knowledge needed to teach science. Another study conducted by Lam, Alviar-Martin, Adler and Sim (2013) reported similar results which showed that teachers' inadequate content knowledge in different subject areas prevented them from identifying key ideas to be covered in teaching an integrated curriculum. Further,

Park (2008) echoed that teachers were not yet well prepared in theoretical knowledge of Integrated Curriculum. As Hinde (2005) noted, successful implementations of IC require skilled and knowledgeable teachers. The complexity of using IC challenges both in-service and pre-service teachers to develop overall teaching competency, including content knowledge in different subject areas, theoretical knowledge on IC, and pedagogical knowledge of implementing integrated curriculum (IC).

3.1 Relationship between Teachers’ Competencies and Learners’ Achievement of Linguistic Skills

The hypothesis of this paper stated that:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ competencies and learners’ achievement of linguistic skills

This hypothesis was tested using Pearson Correlation Coefficient analysis. The results of the analyzed data are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlation Coefficient between Teachers’ Competencies and Learners’ Achievement of Linguistic Skills

	Learner Achievement of Linguistic Skills
Teacher competency	r =.363** p =.000 N= 237

Table 2 shows that there is a positive correlation between teachers’ competencies and learners’ acquisition of linguistic skills ($r=.363$; $p=.000$). This shows that there is a significant relationship between teachers’ competencies and learners’ achievement of linguistic skills, thus the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative accepted. This implied that as teachers’ competencies increased, there was a likelihood of learners' acquisition of linguistic skills. This concurs with the finding of Magoma (2016) who noted that the majority of head teachers under his study noted that teachers of integrated English found curriculum implementation challenging since they had inappropriate training. This shows that the level of training of teachers of Integrated English affects the teaching of integrated English hence the acquisition of linguistic skills among learners.

4.0 Conclusions and Recommendation

The study concluded that teachers' competencies positively influence learners' achievement of linguistic skills showing that enhanced teacher competencies lead to a positive enhancement of linguistic skills; writing, reading, speaking and listening. The study recommended that teachers of English at all levels need to enhance their competencies. This can be done through teacher professional development where the Ministry of Education can provide in-service training to teachers of English on pedagogical issues associated with reading skills in English.

5.0 Implications of the study

The findings and recommendations of this paper may be significant to teachers of English who are the implementers of the curriculum to assist them re-evaluate their styles of teaching and improve on them. It may also assist curriculum planners and developers at Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) on the need to organize in-service courses for teachers of English in line with the revised curriculum. Besides, it may assist the educators in the university and teachers training colleges in preparing the teachers of English curriculum and harmonize their programmes with the changing trends in teaching of English thus allowing for students' achievement of linguistic skills.

6.0 References

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